

The Semantics of Proto-Celtic $*k^w$ enno-: History and Typology

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Abstract

The paper explores the semantic evolution of $*k^w$ enno- ‘head’ reflexes in Celtic languages, tracing their diachronic development and highlighting both language-specific nuances and universal semantic shifts. It describes nine major semantic groups of ‘head’ metaphors and metonymies and devises semantic maps of ‘head’ polysemy in Celtic, Germanic, Romance and Slavic languages. The analysis reveals a trend of the gradual disappearance of anatomical meanings while abstract meanings continue to expand; however, head names retain their usage in spatial and temporal expressions. This study further demonstrates the effectiveness of Celtic languages in lexical typology, owing to their extensive written tradition and the notable semantic distinctions that occasionally emerge among related terms.

0 Publication note

This is a camera-ready version of the paper submitted on 25 November 2014 to be published in the *Proceedings of the First European Symposium in Celtic Studies*, which took place on 5 – 9 August 2013 in Trier, Germany. The book never came out, and this digital publication is the text of the paper as it was sent to the editors after peer-review, except for the title, abstract, formatting, footnotes (2) and (3), acknowledgements and references that required an update (e.g. replacing “in print” with the publication year). Additionally, there was some proofreading that did not impact the content of the paper. The author’s affiliation is cited as of 2013 – 2014.

1 Introduction

This work discusses the inner semantic structure of basic head names in Celtic languages and its diachronic development, pointing out subtle language-specific differences as well as representing universal semantic shifts¹ in the form of semantic maps designed for both Celtic and non-Celtic data. Yet, the results cannot be called fully comprehensive as the material was drawn exclusively from dictionaries, which naturally restricts the context and reduces the number of examples.

Many fundamental works on semantics state the importance of body part terminology, especially from a diachronic perspective. Being “a fundamental reference point of cognition” (Blank and Koch, 1999, p. 6), the human body is highly subject to semantic shifts and innovations and serves as a source domain for grammaticalisation. The head is generally perceived as the main part of the body, which doubles the significance of ‘head’-words² for semantics and cognitive linguistics. Lexemes called “basic head names” in this paper are all reflexes of the Proto-Celtic stem $*k^w$ enno, i.e. Ir. and MIr. *ceann*, OIr. *cenn*, SG. *ceann*, W. and MW. *pen*, Bret. *penn* and Corn. *penn*; other words for ‘head’ like Ir. *cloigeann* are not taken into consideration.³ The oldest attested derivatives of this stem are found in Gaulish and Ogham in-

¹See Zaliznyak (2008) for more information on semantic shifts.

²Hereafter, senses/meanings are enclosed in ‘ ’, while “ ” are used for quotes.

³Languages are abbreviated as follows: **Ir.** – Modern Irish, **SG.** – Scottish Gaelic, **OIr.** – Old Irish, **Og.** – Primitive Irish (the language of the Ogham inscriptions), **W.** – Welsh, **MW.** – Middle Welsh, **Bret.** – Breton, **Corn.** – Cornish, **Gaul.** – Gaulish.

scriptions; they are cited, but not taken into account in broad generalisations as there are very few cases of their occurrence.

The origin of Proto-Celtic **k^w enno-* is obscure: “all attempts to identify a PIE root have proven futile” (Matasović, 2009, p. 177), and no well-grounded substrate etymology has yet been suggested either. Although it is impossible to argue with confidence what particular meaning or meanings the Proto-Celtic **k^w enno-* had due to the absence of evidence, one might still assume that it was already polysemous at that stage. In any case, this study does not attempt to make a semantic reconstruction but merely provides an overview of the meanings the aforementioned stem has developed in different Celtic languages throughout history and analyses how these meanings are organised in comparison with their counterparts in other Indo-European languages. It thus falls into the field of lexical typology, where Celtic material has only recently been introduced, for example, in the works discussing the verbs of rotation (Kruglyakova and Parina, 2010) and animal sounds (Awbery and Parina, 2017).

2 Metaphors and metonymies

It is widely known that two major processes, metonymy and metaphor, supply words with new figurative meanings and cause polysemy. The two groups of ‘head’-metonymies, *totum pro parte* and *pars pro toto*, embrace various examples.

2.1 Totum pro parte

- Ir. *do cheann a bhearradh* ‘to cut one’s hair’;
- W. *pengrych* ‘curly’;
- Corn. *pedn pilez* ‘skinhead’;
- Gaul. *Pennovindos* ‘white-headed’;
- Og. *Qenovendi* ‘white-headed’;
- Ir. *chuir sé an flagún ar a cheann* ‘he raised the flagon to his lips’;
- W. *Cae dy ben!* ‘Shut up!’;
- OIr. *súil glas bannach ina chind* ‘a green lively eye in his face’;
- Bret. *pen ruz* ‘red-faced’.

2.2 Pars pro toto

- Ir. *dá cheann ealaigh* ‘two head of cattle’;
- Mlr. *as a cheann féin* ‘of his own accord’;
- W. *pennau mawr(ion)* ‘important people’;
- Corn. *kettep pen* ‘everyone’;

- Bret. *penn-boesson* ‘drunkard’;
- Ir. *do rogha ceann* ‘whichever you want’;
- Ir. *punt an ceann* ‘a pound each’;
- Ir. *ceann mar é* ‘one like him/it’.

The list of the most common ‘head’-metaphors⁴ in Celtic languages corresponds quite neatly with the general conclusions made by Blank (1998, p. 17 – 18) in his article on ‘head’ in the Romance languages and by Bock et al. (2012, p. 229, 236 – 237) in their study of body part terms in German. These are not the particular senses that are colexified⁵ with ‘head’, but metaphorical concepts underlying colexification, which often produce more than one figurative meaning. For instance, ‘the upper part’ metaphor brought to life such meanings as ‘top’, ‘roof’, ‘upland’, ‘cupola’, ‘heading’, ‘river source’ etc.

2.3 Head as a 3D round object

- Ir. *ceann píopa* ‘bowl of pipe’;
- W. *pen pin* ‘pinhead’;
- W. *pen-ôl* ‘back part, bottom’;
- Bret. *penn kignen* ‘a head of garlic’.

2.4 Head as the seat of mind

- Ir. *thug tú i mo cheann é* ‘you reminded me of it’;
- Ir. *Beir ar cheann ort féin!* “Be sensible!”;
- SG. *chan eil an droch cheann aige* ‘he is not destitute of genius’;
- W. *pendysg* ‘philosophical or theoretical learning (as opposed to experience)’;
- Corn. *pen bronnen* ‘rush-head’;
- Bret. *penn-buoc’h* ‘blockhead’.

2.5 Head as the main / most important part of the body

- Mlr. *cinnréallna* ‘stars of first magnitude’;
- SG. *ceann-aobhair* ‘prime cause’;
- Corn. *pylat o pen iustis* ‘Pilate, who was chief magistrate’;
- Bret. *pennlavarenn* ‘main clause’;
- Bret. *penn-natur* ‘quintessence’.

2.6 Head as the means of control

- Ir. *i gceann ráimha* ‘working with an oar’;
- Ir. *pobal gan cheann* ‘people without a leader’;

⁴Or rather metaphorical concepts, as Lakoff and Johnson (1980) have pointed out.

⁵I.e. lexified identically (François, 2008).

- OIr. *in chinn manach* ‘the abbot’;
- W. *y gwr yw pen y wreic, megis ac y mae Christ yn ben yr Eccles* ‘the man is the head of the woman like Christ is the head of the Church’;
- Corn. *crist pen an syns* ‘Christ, head of the saints’.

2.7 Head as the front part

- Ir. *ceann báid* ‘bows of boat’;
- OIr. *dochuaid i cend in sceoil* ‘went ahead with the tale’.

The last two groups of meanings, which appear to be highly descriptive of space and time mapping in Celtic languages – ‘head as the upper part’ and ‘head as an extremity’ – will be discussed in more detail; while the former is quite universal, the latter might be regarded as a characteristic trait of Celtic languages.⁶

2.8 Head as the upper part

- Ir. *thog tuinn an cinn* ‘waves raised their heads’;
- Ir. *bun os cionn* ‘upside down’;
- SG. *ceann-fhacal* ‘adverb’;
- W. *pen dalen* ‘top of page’;
- MW. *disgyntu a wnaeth Ermin o ben y castell* ‘Ermin came down from the top of the castle’;
- Corn. *war ben vn meneth* ‘on top of a certain mountain’.

As we tend to describe an object’s position correlating it with the human body, the upper part of a vertically oriented object will often be marked as the ‘head’ (Rakhilina, 2008, p. 263 – 264) as in Ir. *ceannbhrat* ‘canopy’, SG. *ceann-tobar* ‘well-cover’, W. *pen y bryn* ‘the summit of the hill’, MW. *disgyntu a wnaeth Ermin o ben y castell* ‘Ermin came down from the top of the castle’. There are several curious cases where ‘head’ means ‘addition’, which reflects the idea of adding as putting something on top of something else: Ir. *i gceann* ‘in addition to’, Bret. *war ar penn* ‘in addition’ or SG. *ceann-fhacal* ‘adverb’, a likely calque from Lat. *adverbum*.

Sometimes, metaphors hidden in particular words or expressions are not so clearly distinguishable, especially if time is in question: thus,

⁶It does not eliminate a possibility that such a semantic shift has happened in some other language(s) as well, but has not been described yet.

the meaning of ‘head’-components in OIr. *ar cinn bliadnae* ‘at the end of the year’ or W. *pen-blwydd* ‘birthday’ is rather inexplicit. However, some Goidelic evidence suggests that the Celtic timeline is not horizontally oriented, but vertically oriented: cf. Ir. *ar mo cheann* ‘awaiting me’ (lit. ‘on my head’), *foi cheann míosa* ‘in a month’ (lit. ‘under head of the month’), and *le trí bliana anuas* ‘for three years’ (lit. ‘with three years from above’), as *sin síos* ‘from then on’ (lit. ‘from that down’). In Early Modern Irish bardic tracts, old case forms are often called *íseal*, ‘low’, and new forms are referred to as *ard* ‘high’, which does not concern stylistic features of these forms but merely describes their age. Yet, creating the Goidelic spatial model of time involves more than just rotating the horizontal ‘forward’ model 90° clockwise or counterclockwise. It is argued to be a spiral rather than a straight line (Mikhaylova, 1995, p. 120 – 122), but this is something that requires further research.

2.9 Head as an extremity

- Ir. *tá dhá cheann ar an scéal* ‘there are two sides of the story’;
- Ir. *dul i geann oibre* ‘to set to work’;
- OIr. *i cind Maige Dála* ‘at the end of Magh Dala’;
- OIr. *forcenn* ‘ending’;
- SG. *a chur ceann air strì* ‘to conclude the strife’;
- SG. *Maol Chinn Tìre* ‘Cape of the Land’s End’;
- W. *penenwad* ‘acrostic’;
- W. *penn-blwydd* ‘birthday’;
- Bret. *penn-ahel* ‘pole’;
- Bret. *pennoù ar bed* ‘the ends of the world’.

In Celtic languages, the head is seen as one of the extremities of the body, a certain point in space where the body begins or ends. This metaphor resulted in such individual meanings as ‘end’, ‘beginning’, and ‘limit, edge’, two of them being products of secondary semantic shifts. At a certain point, there emerges a necessity to contrast the end of a line with the edge of a plane, but as the human body appears to be a rather linear type of object, one might assume that the ‘end’ developed first. A shift from the ‘end’ to the ‘beginning’ must, in turn, be attesting to the opposition between ‘this end’ and ‘the

other end', the latter being the default 'end'.

One of these meanings is attested as early as 731 when Bede the Venerable mentions a Pictish town *Peanfahel*, still existing under the name of *Ceann Fhàil*: "Incipit autem duorum ferme milium spatio a monasterio Aebbercurnig ad occidentem in loco, qui sermone Pictorum Peanfahel, lingua autem Anglorum Penneltun appellatur; et tendens contra occidentem terminatur iuxta urbem Alcluith".⁷ Whatever the origin of the name may be, *pean/ceann* means 'beginning' here. Interestingly enough, this 'beginning' is located on the right as the wall runs westwards. It suggests that this meaning might have derived from 'front part' as well as from 'extremity, end', reflecting the animal-like orientation of horizontal objects (Rakhilina, 2008, p. 264 – 265).

Old Irish bardic terminology gives another significant example of enantiosemey that this word has developed in Celtic languages: poetic devices mentioned by the medieval commentator of *Amra Choluim Chill*⁸:

- *dechned*, 'two-headed': adding an extra ending to the word;
- *díchned*, 'beheading': dropping the last consonant;
- *díchned tuis*, 'beheading of the beginning': dropping the first consonant;
- *cenfochrus*, 'change of head': substituting the first consonant of the word with another one.

Furthermore, there are Ir. *foircheann* 'ending' and W. *penenwad* 'acrostic' where the *ceann/pen* part means 'end' and 'beginning' respectively. The first two examples, *dechned* and *díchned*, are probably indicative of a written word's horizontal animal-like orientation with its 'head' on the right.

3 Semantic maps

Mapping is an important tool for linguistic typology introduced Haspelmath (2003) for making cross-linguistic comparisons in grammatical semantics and later applied to lexical typology by François (2008). Being "a geomet-

rical representation of functions⁹ in 'conceptual/semantic space' that are linked by connecting lines and thus constitute a network" (Haspelmath, 2003, p. 213), semantic maps model the inner semantic structure of a polysemous word, which is, by no means, shapeless or even linear. They embody the following chain algorithm: if language L colexifies senses A and C, it will also colexify senses A and B.

Semantic maps are intended to be universal, i.e., valid for any language, due to having been based on several non-related languages; sometimes the differences within one language family might also be important for creating a reliable semantic map.

A map itself shows primary senses forming an etic grid while the background colour displays how they are attested in a certain group of languages. If they are highlighted, they occur; those marked with a dotted line and a lighter background colour are either peripheral or just restricted to a few examples; some rare meanings and those lying far from the pivot notion are not placed on a map. Sometimes there is more than one path from one sense to another: thus, 'beginning' might have derived from 'front part' (as the Peanfahel example shows) as well as from 'extremity, end'. Figures 1, 2, 3, and 4 are the semantic maps for basic 'head' names in Celtic, Germanic, Romance, and Slavic¹⁰ languages respectively. They present some differences in the extent of these lexemes' polysemy across languages.

Figure 1: Celtic languages.

⁹In lexical typology, functions become senses (François, 2008). Here, 'meaning' is also used as a synonym of 'sense'.

¹⁰The polysemy of head names in Germanic and Slavic languages is thoroughly analysed by Arkadyev (2002); Romance data was derived from Blank (1998).

⁷Bede, *Historia Ecclesiastica Gentis Anglorum*, Lib. I, cap. XII.

⁸The second part of *Rawlinson B 502* manuscript, created in the middle of the 12th century.

Figure 2: Germanic languages.

Figure 3: Romance languages.

Figure 4: Slavic languages.

Although there were no non-Indo-European languages in the focus of this study, it is worth mentioning some typological parallels employed in the semantic map design. In Japanese, ‘head’ colexifies with ‘mind’; ‘person’, ‘something main/the most important’, ‘upper part’ and ‘chief, leader’ (Arkadyev, 2002, p. 13); in Chinese, with ‘beginning’, ‘chief, leader’, ‘emperor’, ‘extremity’, ‘the first page in a book’ and ‘vessel, skull’; in Hebrew, with ‘beginning’, ‘upper part, top’, ‘mind’ and ‘leader’; in Basque, with ‘upper part’ and ‘mind’ (Blank, 1998, p. 25 – 26); and in Egyptian, with ‘upper part’, ‘roof’,

‘beginning’, ‘better part’, ‘chief, leader’, ‘person’, ‘something head-shaped’ and ‘principle’ (Werning, 2014, p. 41).

As the structure of a polysemous word changes throughout time, there are meanings well-attested in old Celtic languages that do not occur (or almost do not occur) in modern ones, and vice versa. A good example of such a historical development is ‘face’: while *cenn* was the basic lexeme for ‘face’ in Old Irish, it has been supplanted by the words *aghaidh* and *éadan* in Modern Irish, which makes a phrase like OIr. *súil glas bannach ina chind* ‘a green lively eye in his face’ impossible for a contemporary Irish speaker. Likewise, we could not find an example in Old Irish or Middle Welsh where ‘head’ would mean ‘mind’.

Meaning distribution in different Celtic languages also varies. The ‘one, item’ sense, which is presumably derived from ‘person/animal’, is widespread in Goidelic languages, while there appears to be no semantic shift in Welsh, Breton, and Cornish that would have allowed ‘head’ to stand for inanimate objects in phrases like Ir. *punt an ceann* ‘a pound each’.

4 Conclusion

The basic head names in Celtic languages display extensive and intricate polysemy, changing their inner structure throughout history by losing and acquiring individual senses.

The analysed examples were organised into nine major semantic groups, excluding some marginal meanings, according to the underlying metaphors and metonymies. While the abstract meaning domain appears to be expanding, a general trend of gradual disappearance was observed in anatomical meanings. While some may argue that modern language speakers perceive the head as the seat of mind rather than a ‘border’ body part, head names are still widely used in spatial and temporal expressions in the sense of ‘top’ or ‘extremity’.

Schematic images of a polysemous word represented as a semantic map might be useful for further research on head names. On the whole, this work serves as another example of how Celtic data proves effective for lexical typology due to the rich long-standing written tradition and sufficient semantic differences that sometimes occur between related words.

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